

Aquatic Symbiosis Genomics Project authorship

The following individuals, representing their Hub teams and their participating institutions, are the key people leading and delivering the Moore Foundation - Wellcome Sanger Institute Aquatic Symbiosis Genomics (ASG) project.

For full details of the ASG project please see

<https://www.sanger.ac.uk/collaboration/aquatic-symbiosis-genomics-project/>.

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